

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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METHODS OF INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF TEACHER WIVES AND GIRLS

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Abstract: This article discusses the social activity of teachers and ways of its formation. Social activity of pedagogical staff is of particular importance in terms of achieving high general and professional culture and competitiveness.

Key words: pedagogical personnel, social activity, didactics, process of formation, ways of formation.

МЕТОДЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ЖЕН И ДЕВУШЕК УЧИТЕЛЕЙ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается социальная активность педагогов и пути ее формирования. Социальная деятельность педагогических кадров имеет особое значение в плане достижения высокой общей и профессиональной культуры и конкурентоспособности.

Ключевые слова: педагогические кадры, общественная деятельность, дидактика, процесс формирования, пути формирования.

INTRODUCTION

In 2022-2026, the national program for increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the economic, political and social life of our country (hereinafter referred to as the National Program) defined the main directions of the state policy to support women.

The national program includes the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan prepared in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On State Policy Regarding Youth", "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence", "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities of Women and Men". The decision "On approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is implemented in accordance with the

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generally recognized principles and norms of international law, international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents.

The main part

Social activity of teaching staff is an understudied problem in didactics. Such activity is changed according to the changes taking place in the social relations of society on the basis of the state order placed before the continuous education system, and acquires a new meaning as the quality of the teacher's personality.

The changes taking place in our society - economic, social, spiritual and educational, and the principles of building a just civil society and a developed legal democratic state require the formation of social activity of pedagogues and raising it to a higher level.

It is known that social activity is a set of actions aimed at satisfying the social needs of a person. The social activity of teachers increases their need for pedagogical activity, helps to approach work creatively, forms professional dignity and pride, and also helps to find their place and position in society, independently in the social and political sphere. It prepares the ground for choosing the right direction.

In order to distinguish the specific criteria of social activity appropriately, teachers should take into account the reform tasks facing the continuous education system in the republic, as well as modern spiritual-educational, political, legal and socio-economic changes. : the meaning of the social and state order placed before the continuous education system and the real level of acquiring the skills of organization and management of the educational process based on modern requirements, awareness of the goals and tasks set for the educational process. their implementation at this stage and in the future; to conduct scientific, scientific-theoretical and methodological research in order to increase continuous self-education; to acquire the skills of rational selection and practical application of modern pedagogical and information technologies that help to form creative thinking and stimulate students' need for self-education; to know the tasks, content, methods and forms of educating students in the spirit of national and universal values, loyalty to the Motherland, cooperation with public organizations; respecting the individual characteristics of students and forming relationships based on the principles of cooperative pedagogy; to know the tasks, content, methods, tools and forms of the educational process carried out in the family and non-school institutions: to be able to apply them in practice; to acquire the skills of effective

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organization of socially useful work, formation of discipline and self-management in the student body; have a high communication culture; formation of new pedagogical thinking; the ability to implement in practical activities; to know the content of important events held in cooperation with international organizations on the implementation of reforms in the field of education and to actively participate in them; environmental, legal, political and non-governmental non-profit organizations, the International Charity Fund, promotion and active participation in events held in our country in order to promote the culture of sanitation and hygiene and promote a healthy lifestyle.

External and internal, objective and subjective factors, characteristics of the teaching and learning process and the microclimate of the educational institution in which he performs his activities help the social activity of the teacher.

In the process of formation of social activity, professional development and retraining courses of pedagogic personnel, which create an opportunity to update and deepen the professional knowledge and skills of professors, play a major role.

As a result of the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to consider the problem of formation of social activity as a leading quality that is inextricably linked with professional training. The social activity of the teacher affects professional training and the desire to expand scientific outlook, deepen knowledge in methodology, pedagogy, psychology, specialization, as well as acquire skills and abilities for effective work. appears. Social activity and professional training of teachers is a closely related and interconnected process.

The formation of necessary qualities in the profession prepares the ground for the development of high social activity in the teacher, as well as ensures the objective necessity of mastering special, psychological, pedagogical, methodological knowledge and organizational skills.

If the social activity of the teacher is combined with his spiritual-educational, psychological and intellectual professional training and creates a favorable psychological environment for the implementation of the tasks and goals of the educational process and the state standard, then the professional training and received they themselves become direct participants and self-developing subjects, excluding internal contradictions between knowledge, skills and competences.

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In our republic, professional development of professors and teachers is carried out through the system of state institutions - professional development institutes (central and regional), relevant faculties of higher educational institutions, regional methodical offices of public education departments. Each of these departments has its own characteristics, but the goal is common: to effectively deliver advanced pedagogical experience to every teacher, to ignite sparks of creativity and interest in work, to reveal the essence and technology of a particular experience.

Students of republican courses are given a task after the course - to creatively use the elements of the learned experience in their practice and introduce them to teachers in their region. As a rule, local course participants are leaders of creative groups and promoters of their ideas on the subject of the mastered experience, where their social activity is manifested.

The results of our experience on the formation and development of social activity of teachers in professional development courses and the analysis of the literature show that the following can be achieved: clearly defining long-term plans for the development of social activity, effective and timely use. new pedagogical and information technologies in the classroom; creating conditions for acquiring professional skills, abilities and types of mental activity; independent and creative thinking; acquire the ability to analyze various problem situations; self-education and self-development organizations; organization of effective self-education of students in independent work with educational, methodological, scientific-popular and additional literature; daily mental work and research; establishing conscious discipline as a quality of personality; formation of analytical-critical, creative and independent thinking, mastering advanced pedagogical technologies and awakening the need for their creation, increasing professional training by developing professional knowledge and skills; in cooperation with educational institutions, neighborhoods, the International Charity Fund, non-governmental non-profit organizations, to form a healthy lifestyle, to guide students to active participation in order to raise moral-political, legal, ecological and sanitary culture.

SUMMARY

Effective organization of the educational process in teacher training courses to satisfy the need for students to have a conscious attitude to learning, to develop the skills of research, independent analysis, and to regularly replenish the level of self-education forms responsibility in conducting research for; plays an important

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role in the formation of social activity and, most importantly, in increasing professional training.

During the transition to a new stage of Uzbekistan's development, it is important to raise the system of comprehensive support for all women to a higher level, to further increase the place and role of women in society.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Касимова, О. Х. (2023). Роль Инновационных Технологий В Качественной Организации Образовательного Процесса Женщин-Педагогов. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 397-401.
2. Касимова, О. Х. (2023). Роль Женщин И Девушек-Педагогов В Развитии Мышления Молодежи. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 389-392.
3. Касимова, О. Х. (2023). Повышение Социальной Активности Женщин-Учителей–Веление Времени. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 393-396.
4. Xudonazarovna, Q. O., & Sunnatillo o'g'li, V. H. (2022). The Teacher is National in Increasing the Social Activity of Women and the Combination of Foreign Experience. *Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences*, 1(6), 129-132.
5. Касимова Озода Худойназаровна, & Норммахматова Адолат Шавкат қизи. (2023). Повышение Социальной Активности Женщин-Учителей – Веление Времени. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 393–396. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/1721>
6. Касимова Озода Худойназаровна, & Яндашова Дилшода Одилжон қизи. (2023). Роль Женщин И Девушек-Педагогов В Развитии Мышления Молодежи. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 389–392. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/1720>
7. Касимова Озода Худойназаровна, & Холмуминова Васида Хамдам қизи. (2023). Роль Инновационных Технологий В Качественной Организации Образовательного Процесса Женщин-Педагогов. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 397–401. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/1722>

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8. THE NEED TO DEVELOP THE TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. (2023). International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(6), 181-186. <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/2050>
9. Utanov, U. (2023). THE USE OF ANCESTRAL HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture, 3(6), 95–100. Retrieved from <https://internationalbulletins.com/intjour/index.php/jah/article/view/819>
10. Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich, I. M. F. qizi . (2023). PERIODS OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK MUSICOLOGY. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(6), 320–324. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019906>
11. Курбонович, У. У. ., & Абдурахмонович, . А. А. . . . (2023). МУСИҚИЙ ТЎГАРАКЛАР ВОСИТАСИДА ЎҚУВЧИ ЁШЛАРНИ БАДИИЙ-ЕСТЕТИК ТАРБИЯЛАШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ШАРТ- ШАРОИТЛАРИ. FAN, TA'LIM VA AMALIYOTNING INTEGRASIYASI, 571-580. Retrieved from <https://journal.bilig.uz/isepsmj/article/view/1234>
12. У, У. . (2023). ЎҚИТУВЧИ МАЪНАВИЙ ҚИЁФАСИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШГА ДОИР. FAN, TA'LIM VA AMALIYOTNING INTEGRASIYASI, 580-583. Retrieved from <https://journal.bilig.uz/isepsmj/article/view/1235>
13. Курбонович, У. У. ., & Акбар қизи, Х. Л. . (2023). МУСИҚАНИНГ ТИББИЁТДА ТУТГАН ЎРНИ ҲАМДА УНИНГ ИНСОН РУҲИЯТИ ВА СОҒЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. FAN, TA'LIM VA AMALIYOTNING INTEGRASIYASI, 584-589. Retrieved from <https://journal.bilig.uz/isepsmj/article/view/1236>
14. Socio-pedagogical analysis of the development of the spiritual image of a person. (2023). Boletin De Literatura Oral - The Literary Journal, 10(1), 2230-2238. <https://www.boletindeliteraturaoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/481>